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PERCEIVE

**Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Colored collections
through AI and Virtual Experiences**

D8.3. PERCEIVE Publications and Demonstrators

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4	NTNU	Norges Teknisk-Naturvitenskapelige Universitet	Norway
5	FRAUNHOFER	Fraunhofer Gesellschaft Zur Forderung Der Angewandten Forschung	Germany
6	MIC-MANN	Ministry of Cultural Heritage- National Archaeological Museum of Naples	Italy
7	OSL-MUNCH	Oslo Kommune Munch Museum (MUNCH)	Norway
8	AIC	The Art Institute of Chicago	USA
9	HOVERLAY	Hoverlay	USA
10	HSLU	Fachhochschule Zentralschweiz -Hochschule Luzern	Switzerland
11	V&A	Victoria and Albert Museum	UK

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Executive summary

PERCEIVE aims at creating a new way to preserve, perceive, curate, exhibit, understand, and access colored Cultural Heritage collections and Digital Artworks. By promoting their re-appropriation, the project addresses the high fragility of these collections, the complexity of their study, and the significance of their proper communication to future generations. This Deliverable 8.3 documents the consolidated dissemination outcomes of the project, encompassing the publication of open-access scientific volumes and the organization of the final hybrid events. Rather than a single standalone venue, the project adopted a cluster approach to scientific dissemination, coordinating workshops, exhibitions, and demonstrator showcases across multiple partner locations and international forums.

The primary outcomes detailed in this document include:

- **Scientific Publications:** The project produced "Chromatic Visions: Exploring Colour in Art, Archaeology, and Digital Realities," divided into two open-access volumes. Volume 1 was published in November 2025, and Volume 2 is scheduled for 2026. Additionally, the exhibition catalogue "Perceive Isis' Colours" was published in September 2025.
- **Scientific Conferences:** The main scientific event was integrated into the Digital Heritage World Congress 2025 in Siena (September 2025), featuring the thematic session "Exhibiting the Unexhibitable" and a dedicated expo space for tools and prototypes. Additional events included the "Fragile Colours" conference at the Victoria and Albert Museum and pre-event participation at InART2024 and SITEM 2025.
- **Hybrid Exhibitions and Prototypes:** A series of exhibitions implemented the project's "Caring," "Authenticity," and "Open Space Museum" prototypes across Europe:
 - **"Perceive Isis' Colours":** Featuring the "Echoes of Loss" and "The Gifts of Isis" installations, this exhibition was presented at Digital Heritage 2025 in Siena, ArcheoVirtual 2025 in Paestum, and permanently relocated to Manifattura Tabacchi in Florence.
 - **"Tiny Conservators":** An interactive caring prototype and cooperative game presented at the MUNCH Museum in Oslo in December 2025.
 - **"Fragile Colours":** An exhibition focused on autochromes held at the NTNU Vitenskapsmuseet in Trondheim from November 2025 to October 2026.
 - **The Open Space Museum (OSM):** Deployed as "A Ticket to the Moon" in Zürich and as the "PERCEIVE Parcour" in Rotkreuz, testing social engagement and modular exhibition frameworks in public spaces.
- **Catalogue of Demonstrators:** A web-based collection of tools, services, and prototypes produced by WP5 and WP6 has been made accessible, supporting the transfer of methodologies for studying and communicating color to the wider heritage sector.

This final version of the deliverable, released at M36, provides a comprehensive account of these activities, demonstrating how PERCEIVE has successfully bridged high-level research with user-friendly digital solutions and public engagement. It represents the description of the main dissemination outcomes of the project, that includes the publication of open access scientific book, divided into two volumes, containing the results of the project, and the organization of final hybrid events, encompassing Scientific conferences and Public hybrid exhibitions

Document History

Version	Release date	Summary of changes	Author(s) -Institution
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V0.2	20/01/2024	Second draft	Sofia Pescarin, Ivana Cerato, Federica Bonifazi CNR ISPC
V0.3	31/01/2024	Final version of the deliverable	Sofia Pescarin, Ivana Cerato, Federica Bonifazi CNR ISPC
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V0.5	09/02/2024	Third revision of the Deliverable and third iteration of revision	Sofia Pescarin CNR ISPC, All partners
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V2.0	24/11/2025	First Draft with new chapters included	Sofia Pescarin, CNR ISPC
V3.0	27/12/2025	Final Draft with new chapters and reorganisation	Ivana Cerato, Federica Bonifazi, Sofia Pescarin, CNR ISPC, All partners
V4.0	30/01/2026	Final version of the deliverable containing the results of the tasks	Ivana Cerato, Federica Bonifazi, and all partners

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1. PERCEIVE Publication

1.1 Publication plan

As part of WP8, the publication plan for two forthcoming open access books arising from the PERCEIVE project was established. The books, published by Springer are titled “**Chromatic Visions: Exploring Colour in Art, Archaeology, and Digital Realities**”. The first volume has been published in November 2025, the second in 2026 and explore more technical themes and aspects of PERCEIVE. The editors decided to write internally the two volumes and once ready to send for review them to the external experts (the PERCEIVE Scientific Advisory Board) for approval. The editors then re-engage with the authors and prepare the final revised chapters. The editors have also deliberated that the book is published under an Open Access license. Beyond these two volumes, the project has published also the catalogue of the exhibition “Perceive Isis’ Colours”

1.2 Book: Volume 1

“**Chromatic Visions: Exploring Colour in Art, Archaeology and Digital Realities. Part 1**” has been published by Elsevier

This open access book explores the challenges and opportunities of preserving, reconstructing, exhibiting, and communicating the phenomenon of colour change in heritage collections and artworks through advanced digital technologies, from the perspectives of the authors, many of whom belong to renowned institutions around Europe. Developed within the Horizon Europe project PERCEIVE, this is the first of two volumes offering a comprehensive, interdisciplinary approach to chromatic heritage.

Home > Book

Chromatic Visions

Exploring Colour in Art, Archaeology and Digital Realities, Part I

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Overview

Editors: [Sofia Pescarin](#), [Cristiana Barandoni](#), [Arthur Clay](#), [George Papadopoulos](#), [Irina Crina Anca Sandu](#)

- This book is open access, which means that you have free and unlimited access
- Develops a theoretical framework dedicated to colour perception and to cognitive and emotional goals
- Shows how to preserve, reconstruct, exhibit and communicate the colours of original cultural heritage artworks
- Related to EU Horizon 2020 PERCEIVE project

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Figure 1: Screen capture of website with the download or buy option for *Chromatic Visions Vol. 1* (<https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-032-07792-9>)

Focusing on perception, historical transformations of colour, digital heritage design, and civic participation, the book introduces five key scenarios: from ancient polychrome sculpture and paintings to textiles, historical photographs, and digital-born artworks. Through these, it investigates how colour can be experienced, interpreted, and cared for in both physical and virtual spaces.

Combining scientific investigations and concept-oriented design, the volume presents new methodologies based on the concepts of care, authenticity, civic participation and accessibility. It is an essential resource for researchers, curators, designers, and all those engaged in the digital transformation of cultural heritage.

The book has been published in Open Access and it is freely accessible at:
<https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-032-07792-9>

Table of contents include:

- [Perception](#) Yoko Arteaga, Vanessa Bonanno, Peter Nussbaum, Delfina Sol Martinez Pandiani, Sofia Pescarin, Sophia Sotiropoulou
- [Colour Through Time](#) Irina Crina Anca Sandu, Cristiana Barandoni, Letizia Monico, Arthur Clay, Irina Mihaela Ciortan, Brenda Doherty et al.
- [Authenticity in the Design of Digital Heritage Applications](#) Sofia Pescarin, Ivana Cerato, Irina-Mihaela Ciortan, Giuseppe Città, Arthur Clay, Samuele Spotti et al.
- [Sense of Care in the Design of Digital Heritage Applications](#) Manuele Veggi, Vanessa Bonanno, Ivana Cerato, Irina-Mihaela Ciortan, Arthur Clay, Gabriele Fiorenza et al.
- [Extending Civic Participation \(in Public Spaces\)](#) Arthur Clay, Vanessa Bonanno, Federica Bonifazi, Chiara Gemma Fedon, Sofia Pescarin
- [Colour Fragility](#) Cristiana Barandoni, Lucia Burgio, Arthur Clay, Brenda Doherty, Chiara Gemma Fedon, Roberta Iannaccone et al.
- [Designing Coloured Experiences](#) Sofia Pescarin, Cristiana Barandoni, Vanessa Bonanno, Ivana Cerato, Daniele Ferdani, Donata Magrini et al.

1.3 Book: Volume 2

“Chromatic Visions: Exploring Colour in Art, Archaeology and Digital Realities. Part 2” is being published by Elsevier

This open access book builds upon the conceptual foundations established in the first part, presenting practical methods, tools, and workflows for studying and communicating colour in cultural heritage.

Developed within the Horizon Europe project PERCEIVE, this second volume examines how scientific analysis, digital reconstruction, and interactive design can be integrated into reproducible workflows. It documents the operational frameworks, technological infrastructures, and design resources developed to study, model, visualise, and communicate colour change across diverse heritage collections.

Structured around three complementary chapters (scientific modelling of colour change, digital tools and services for knowledge sharing, and design resources for interactive experiences) the book presents advanced workflows, AI-assisted methods, FAIR data infrastructures, and participatory exhibition prototypes. Case studies range from ancient polychromy and paintings to textiles, photography, and born-digital art, demonstrating approaches to make colour research accessible and transparent for both specialists and broader audiences.

Grounded in principles of care, authenticity, and participation, Chromatic Visions II addresses digital heritage as both a technical and relational practice. The book provides researchers, conservators, curators, designers, and museum professionals with methods and frameworks for interdisciplinary approaches to the digital study and communication of coloured collections.

The book, edited by I.-M. Ciortan, D. Ferdani, J. Y. Hardeberg and M. Veggi, will be published within March 2026 as an open access volume of Springer Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS) Series:
<https://link.springer.com/book/9783032176998>.

Table of contents include:

- Methods and Workflows for Colour Change Modelling and Reconstruction -
Yoko Arteaga, Cristiana Barandoni, Lucia Burgio, David Buti, Irina-Mihaela Ciortan, Brenda Doherty, Jon Yngve Hardeberg, Catlin Langford, Donata Magrini, Catarina Pinto, Irina Crina Anca Sandu, Faïçal Selka, Saptarshi Neil Sihna, Panagiotis Siozos, Sophia Sotiropoulou, Giorgio Trumpy
- Tools and Services for Colour Change Analysis and Sharing of Knowledge
Irina-Mihaela Ciortan, Bruno Fanini, Paul Julius Kühn, Marcello Massidda, Paschalis Panteleris, George Papadopoulos, Marios Pitikakis, Saptarshi Neil Sihna, Panagiotis Siozos, Sophia Sotiropoulou, Petros Ioannis Stavroulakis, Giorgio Trumpy
- Design Resources to Enhance Access to Coloured Collections through Interactive Experiences
Marcello Massidda, Birgitte Aga, Cristiana Barandoni, Federica Bonifazi, Ivana Cerato, Arthur Clay, Enzo D'Annibale, Bruno Fanini, Daniele Ferdani, Marialucia Giacco, Roberta Iannaccone, Donata Magrini, Caterina Serena Martucci, Nynne Ryhl Olsson, Irina Crina Anca Sandu, Samuele Spotti, Laura Travaglini, Giorgio Trumpy, Sofia Pescarin and Manuele Veggi

1.4 Catalogue: Perceive Isis' Colours

Another volume was published as an open access catalogue of one of the exhibitions organised during the Final Hybrid Events program. This volume offers a thorough examination of the exhibition "Perceive Isis' Colours", which investigates the convergence of technology, archaeology, and cultural heritage through the lens of the Temple of Isis in Pompeii. The forewords establish a framework for a multidisciplinary approach aimed at understanding and reconstructing the vibrant chromatic attributes of ancient artworks. Chapter 1 delineates the innovative design and objectives of the exhibition, underscoring the critical role of colour in the interpretation of classical heritage. Chapter 2 provides an in-depth analysis of the historical significance of the Temple of Isis, elaborating on its archaeological context and the intricate details of its polychromatic decorations. In Chapter 3, the authors articulate the dual structure of the exhibition, which integrates educational and immersive experiences to foster a deeper engagement with the historical narrative. Chapter 4 addresses the multifaceted challenges encountered throughout the project, exploring the complexities associated with colour reconstruction. Chapter 5 presents a comprehensive overview of the PERCEIVE project, which seeks to combine the understanding of polychromy with the application of advanced digital technologies to communicate it. Finally, chapter 6 concludes with a forward-looking discussion on the future of colour in heritage studies, emphasizing the necessity for ongoing innovation and collaborative efforts within the field.

The book, edited by C. Barandoni, S. Pescarin, M.L. Giacco, C.S. Martucci has been published in September 2025 as an open access volume of Museo Archeologico Nazionale di Napoli (MANN), published by Valtrend Editori and freely available on line, at link: <https://www.valtrent.it/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/Preceive-Isis-Colours.pdf>

The catalogue resulted as the effort combination by CNR and MANN which participated in content writing, image selection, documentary apparatus, and curatorial texts. Through this editorial contribution, the museum facilitated the international dissemination of project results towards scholars, practitioners, and stakeholders in museum and heritage policy, thanks to the exhibition being displayed during DigitalHeritage 2025 world event in Siena.

Table of Content

- Forewords (M. Osanna, C. Miliani)
- Chapter 1. The exhibition (M. Giacco, S. Pescarin)
- Chapter 2. The temple of Isis (C.S. Martucci, C. Barandoni)

- Chapter 3. Two Sections, One Experience (F. Bonifazi, M. Massidda, S. Pescarin)
- Chapter 4. The Challenges (C. Barandoni, F. Bonifazi, I. Cerato, D. Ferdani, D. Magrini, S. Spotti, M. Veggi)
- Chapter 5. PERCEIVE (S. Pescarin, C. Barandoni)
- Chapter 6. Conclusions: the future of colour (C. Barandoni, M. Giacco, S. Pescarin)

Figure 2: Screen capture of website with the download option for the catalogue PERCEIVE Isis' Colours (<https://www.valtrend.it/product/perceive-isis-colours/>)

1.5 PERCEIVE Scientific Publications

In this chapter we list a selection of the most relevant publications in scientific journals and presented in scientific international venues.

2023 Massidda, M., Travaglini, L., & Pescarin, S. (2023). Interactive digital narrative authoring tools and hybrid experiences in cultural heritage. An integrated review. In Eurographics Workshop on Graphics and Cultural Heritage (pp. 31-35). Eurographics Association.

2023 Pescarin, S., Cerato, I., d'Annibale, E., Fanini, B., Ferdani, D., Del Fà, R. M., ... & Ronchi, D. (2023, September). Hybrid XR Collaborative and Guided Experiences in Cultural Heritage: Brancacci POV Prototype. In GCH (pp. 157-161).

2024 Ciortan, I. M., & Trumpy, G. (2024, April). FILM2PAINT: Transforming Photographic Documentation on Reversal Film into Paintings' Accurate Colors. In Archiving Conference (Vol. 21, pp. 17-22). Society for Imaging Science and Technology.

2024 Ciortan, I. M., Trumpy, G., & Sandu, I. C. A. (2024). The Scream (ca. 1910) through the Years: from Photographic Documentation to Digital Rejuvenation. Colour Photography and Film: Sharing knowledge of analysis, preservation, and, 152.

- 2024 Ciortan, I. M., Trumpy, G., & Sandu, I. C. A. (2024). The Scream (ca. 1910) through the Years: from Photographic Documentation to Digital Rejuvenation. *Colour Photography and Film: Sharing knowledge of analysis, preservation, and*, 152.
- 2024 Massidda, M., Bordignon, A., Fabbri, F., Nori, R., Piccardi, L., Travaglini, L., ... & Pescarin, S. (2024). Towards an Experiment Planner for Cognitive Studies in Virtual Heritage Environments. A Pilot Study. In *Eurographics workshop on graphics and cultural heritage*. The Eurographics Association. <https://doi.org/10.2312/gch> (Vol. 20241261).
- 2024 Pescarin, Sofia, Giuseppe Città, and Samuele Spotti. "Authenticity in interactive experiences." *Heritage* 7.11 (2024): 6213-6242.
- 2024 Sinha, S. N., Gorschlueter, F., Graf, H., & Weinmann, M. (2024, September). Deepmaterialinsights: A web-based framework harnessing deep learning for estimation, visualization, and export of material assets from images. In *Proceedings of the 29th International ACM Conference on 3D Web Technology* (pp. 1-5).
- 2024 Sinha, S. N., Kühn, J., Graf, H., & Weinmann, M. (2024, September). Spectralsplatsviewer: An interactive web-based tool for visualizing cross-spectral gaussian splats. In *Proceedings of the 29th International ACM Conference on 3D Web Technology* (pp. 1-10).
- 2024 Sinha, S. N., Kühn, P. J., Koppe, J., Graf, H., & Weinmann, M. (2024, October). Digital Restoration of Visual Art using Synthetic Training, Deep Segmentation and inpainting. In *2024 International Conference on Cyberworlds (CW)* (pp. 338-339). IEEE.
- 2024 Sinha, S. N., Kühn, P. J., Rojtberg, R., Graf, H., Kuijper, A., & Weinmann, M. (2024). Semantic Stylization and Shading via Segmentation Atlas utilizing Deep Learning Approaches. In *2024 Eurographics Italian Chapter Conference on Smart Tools and Applications in Graphics, STAG 2024* (p. 20241352). Eurographics Association.
- 2025 Ananiadou, E., Pescarin, S., Gkiokas, A., Kolek, L., Penuela, A. M., Neagu, D. A., ... & Tempesta, P. L. (2025). Data Collection and Reuse in Digital Heritage: Approaches and Results from the Digital Cultural Heritage Cluster.
- 2025 Barandoni, C., Burgio, L., Clay, A., Doherty, B., Fedon, C. G., Iannaccone, R., ... & Trumpy, G. (2025). Colour Fragility. In *Chromatic Visions: Exploring Colour in Art, Archaeology and Digital Realities, Part I* (pp. 184-222). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- 2025 Bonifazi, F., Veggi, M., Massidda, M., Ferdani, D., & Pescarin, S. (2025). Implementing Curiosity Hooks and Caring Practices in the Reconstruction of Lost Polychromy: Design Prototypes for Interactive Experiences. In *EUROGRAPHICS WORKSHOP ON GRAPHICS AND CULTURAL HERITAGE*.
- 2025 Ciortan, I., Arteaga, Y., & Trumpy, G. (2025). Silver/dyes decoupling and colour restoration of autochromes using multispectral imaging. *The European Physical Journal Plus*, 140(5), 384.
- 2025 Fanini, B., Massidda, M., Ferdani, D., Bonifazi, F., Magrini, D., Iannaccone, R., & Barandoni, C. (2025). Interactive and immersive discovery of diagnostic processes on multi-layered 3D collections on the web: the MuLaX tool. In *Digital Heritage*.
- 2025 Ferdani, D., Barandoni, C., Bonifazi, F., Iannaccone, R., & Magrini, D. (2025). Multiband photogrammetry for multispectral 3D reconstruction of statuary. *Journal of Cultural Heritage*, 76, 74-85.
- 2025 Massidda, M., Fanini, B., & Sofia, P. (2025). Prototyper: a web3D platform for collaborative design and simulation of hybrid museum exhibitions. In *Digital Heritage*.

- 2025 Pescarin, S., Aga, B., Fanini, B., Fedon, G. C., Ferdani, D., Graf, H., ... & Clay, A. (2025). Perceptive enhanced realities of coloured collections through AI and virtual experiences. In EUROGRAPHICS WORKSHOP ON GRAPHICS AND CULTURAL HERITAGE.
- 2025 Sinha, S. N., Ciortan, I. M., Kneiphof, T., Kühn, P. J., Doherty, B., Burgio, L., ... & Weinmann, M. (2025). An Atlas-based Approach for Appearance-aware Virtual 3D Restoration and Simulation of Fading in Fugitive Textiles. In Digital Heritage International Congress 2025.
- 2025 Sinha, S. N., Horst, R., Ciortan, I. M., Graf, H., Kuijper, A., & Weinmann, M. (2025, March). ImmersiveAutochrome: Enhanced Digitized Mono-Autochrome Viewing through Deep Learning and Virtual Reality. In 2025 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces Abstracts and Workshops (VRW) (pp. 29-34). IEEE.
- 2025 Siozos, P., Monico, L., Romani, A., Miliani, C., Doherty, B., Sandu, I. C. A., ... & Sotiropoulou, S. (2025). Light source classification and colour change modelling for understanding and predicting pigments discolouration. *Journal of Physics: Photonics*.
- 2025 Stavroulakis, P. I., Pagano, A., Boracchi, B., Siozos, P., Sotiropoulou, S., Leonhardt, E., ... & Sandu, I. C. (2025). Tactile 3D-printed media interaction with the color surface features of paintings. The case of the Scream (1910?) painting. *Frontiers in Computer Science*, 7, 1597880.
- 2025 Travaglini, L., Massidda, M., Zapf, A., Spotti, S., Veggi, M., & Pescarin, S. (2025, June). The CoDesign Tool. A Card-Based Framework for Interactive and Collaborative Design in Cultural Heritage. In *International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction* (pp. 276-297). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- 2025 Veggi, M., & Pescarin, S. (2025). Participatory Experiences as a New Way to Access Conservation Data in Museum Contexts. *Mimesis Journal* vol. 13, n. 2: Scritture della performance, (2), 95.
- 2025 Veggi, M., Von Gal, A., Piccardi, L., Pescarin, S., & Nori, R. (2025). How much do we care about cultural heritage? a rasch scale validation study among young adults. *Heritage*, 8(8), 317.

2. PERCEIVE hybrid events

During the project, an hybrid final events programme has been planned, open to citizens, the scientific community and industries, with the goal of encompassing scientific conferences, public exhibitions (tangible and digital), and online demos. The events were meant to be the main venues where tools, services (WP5) and prototypes (WP6) could be accessible to the wider community of stakeholders. These outcomes are part of the PERCEIVE Catalogue of Demonstrators. All outcomes have been evaluated by WP7.

PERCEIVE Hybrid Event has been planned around:

1. Final **scientific events** on coloured collections and their study, reconstruction, conservation and communication. The events have been organised during the DigitalHeritage 2025 conference, the Fragile Colour exhibition in Trondheim and at the Victoria & Albert Museum. During these events the results and outcomes of PERCEIVE have been presented, including the methodology, AI core, the tools and services, the prototypes. The events have organised physically, while remote participation was in some cases granted. Target users involved have been the scientific community, cultural heritage institutions, policy makers, and creative industries. To support the uptakes of PERCEIVE results, specific tutorials have been organised before, during, and after the events.

2. **Final hybrid exhibitions**, organised in physical locations (Basel, Siena, Firenze, Trondheim, Oslo), with original or reproduced elements of collections and with digital applications complementing the visit. The exhibitions have targeted to European citizens (and specifically schools, families, groups of friends), including also experts in the domain. These exhibitions included physical installations along with digital applications, conceived and built by using PERCEIVE the tools and services.
3. A remote virtual exhibition was initially planned, but the project scientific board decided to give a priority to the hybrid exhibitions. Nevertheless, online demos of the tools and services have been organised, and are now accessible through the YouTube channel of the project (https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PLN0wRQbI_QqDHOw7QekPnoEg3tFX5qbNh&si=xATMcPH0NymCVzcC), divided into specific webinars carried out within the WP2 activities (D. 2.3) Target audience of these demos have been the experts in conservation science, designers and ICT specialists.

2.1 Other demo events (2024-2025)

2.1.1 InART demonstrators (June 2024)

Format: Conference participation and demonstrator activity (incl. pre-conference workshop)

Date: 3–7 June 2024

Place: Oslo, Norway (InART2024 – International Conference on Innovation in Art Research and Technology)

Audience: Heritage science researchers; conservators; scientists; museum professionals; cultural heritage stakeholders

Concept

In June 2024, PERCEIVE contributed to InART2024, a conference hosted by the University of Oslo that brings together natural sciences and conservation to foster interdisciplinary exchange on central topics in heritage science research. As part of the PERCEIVE dissemination activities, the project featured demonstrator-oriented presentation moments and stakeholder engagement during the conference days (4–7 June 2024). A dedicated pre-conference workshop was organised on 3 June 2024 entitled “Colour and appearance for cultural heritage – new research approaches from the ApPEARS and PERCEIVE projects”. The workshop presented and discussed ongoing research approaches from the NETApP (NFR-funded) and PERCEIVE (EU-funded) projects and was framed as a collaboration involving researchers from Colourlab (NTNU) and the Munch Museum.

Fig.3 Exhibition of the PERCEIVE Demonstrators during inART24

Demonstrators in connection with the Open Space Museum prototype included:

- **Open Space Museum Sketch Book**
 Material: Paper and acrylic glass
 Dimensions: H 2 cm; W 30 cm; L 50 cm
 Placement: On a table
 Lighting: Standard room lighting
 Description: The Sketch Book documents methods developed for the Case Study Elements of the Open Space Museum, including strategies for guiding visitors through PERCEIVE colour collections and supporting engagement aligned with the project's key concepts (e.g., authenticity and care).
- **Autochrome Demonstrator**
 Material: Acrylic glass, UV prints, electronics
 Dimensions: H 55 cm; W 50 cm; L 130 cm
 Placement: On a table
 Lighting: Standard room lighting
 Description: The demonstrator communicates the layered material logic of autochromes, including the coloured starch mosaic and how layering contributes to colour image formation. It also illustrates approaches for reconstructing missing information in degraded plates by re-layering and re-assembling image components.
- **VR CHROMA – OSM Prototype Demonstrator for Born Digital Arts**
 Material: VR headset
 Dimensions: approx. 15 × 7 × 20 cm
 Placement: On a table
 Lighting: Standard room lighting

Description: This demonstrator presents PERCEIVE Scenario 5 (Born Digital Art) by allowing visitors to explore selected AR artworks inside a VR environment. The experience includes navigation through a virtual scene featuring OSM-related structures and curated born-digital content, including an outer-space constellation gallery.

- **VR CHROMA – Open Space Museum Demonstrator**

Material: VR headset

Dimensions: approx. 15 × 7 × 20 cm

Placement: On a table

Lighting: Standard room lighting

Description: The VR demonstrator “CHROMA” visualises the Chroma Elements of the Open Space Museum by integrating real/physical design ideas with virtual representations. It features the Chroma Tower and AR Portal elements and offers two modes (day and night), where lighting and multi-texturing communicate how colour appearance changes under different viewing conditions, including a Space Art Gallery nightscape.

2.1.2 PERCEIVE Parcour (December 2024)

Format: Exhibition (parcour / station-based pathway)

Date: 9–10 December 2024

Place: Hochschule Luzern – Informatik, Campus Zug-Rotkreuz, Suurstoffi 1 (Building B), 6343 Rotkreuz, Switzerland

Audience: Researchers in Art, Design, and Informatics; students; general public.

Concept.

The PERCEIVE Parcour is a curated, spatial exhibition format designed to test the orchestration and sequencing of multiple PERCEIVE demonstrators within a single coherent pathway. Visitors follow a defined route between stations, engaging with each demonstrator in sequence and allowing time for reflection between encounters. Movement and transition are treated as integral components of the experience, supporting dialogue, comparison, and deeper attention to each station. Within the PERCEIVE dissemination strategy, the Parcour functioned as a structured field test for combining heterogeneous demonstrators—digital, physical, and hybrid—into a unified spatial narrative. In addition to public engagement, the format provided a suitable framework for structured evaluation through surveys, supporting iterative refinement of demonstrators and dissemination approaches.

Demonstrators included the following stations/modules:

- **The SCREAM Demonstrator:**
A multisensory demonstrator translating colour-difference perception into an alternative experience through light- and sound-based cues.
- **The AUTOCHROME Demonstrator:**
An optical viewing demonstrator presenting the reconstruction and interpretation of autochrome material through layered image access.
- **VR CHROMA Project (Born Digital Art demonstrator):**
A VR demonstrator presenting PERCEIVE’s born-digital art scenario and related XR content as an immersive exploration.

- **The Aljosa Box (demonstrator for modular and hybrid design practices):**
A tangible demonstrator communicating principles of modular assembly and hybrid exhibition logic in a compact object format.
- **The SPACE ART Gallery Demonstrator:**
A demonstrator presenting curated digital and animated content assets within the PERCEIVE dissemination framework.
- **The Open Space Museum Sketch Book / Design Book:**
A design artefact communicating the Open Space Museum (OSM) concept, spatial logic, and modular structure through drawings and explanatory material.
- **Gabinetto Segreto (hybrid light and projection object):**
A compact acrylic-glass object with integrated lighting and projection, reinterpreting the Gabinetto experience through an intimate viewing format.

Evaluation and Monitoring

To support the assessment of the PERCEIVE Parcours as a dissemination and engagement activity, a set of evaluation instruments was deployed during the exhibition. These included a general observation survey covering the entire Parcours, as well as demonstrator-specific questionnaires corresponding to the individual HSLU demonstrators. The surveys were administered by a team of five trained staff members who followed shared guidelines and received preparatory training prior to the exhibition. The evaluation approach was primarily qualitative and supported by structured categorical indicators, and was used to document visitor engagement, interaction patterns, and high-level dissemination outcomes. The evaluation activities supported iterative refinement of the demonstrators and informed future dissemination strategies. The complete set of survey instruments used during the PERCEIVE Parcours is provided in the annexes.

Lessons Learned

The Parcours format proved effective for disseminating PERCEIVE outcomes through sequential, station-based engagement and supported social discussion around the demonstrators. Several practical lessons were identified to strengthen future Parcours deployments:

- Onboarding at threshold stations: technically complex stations (especially immersive/interactive interfaces) benefit from clearer entry cues (simple “what to do” prompts and visual guidance).
- Flow and bottleneck management: high-demand stations require queue-aware spatial layout and optional “parallel engagement” elements to reduce perceived waiting and maintain overall parcours momentum.
- Consistency of mediation: shared briefing points and concise station scripts help ensure a coherent narrative across heterogeneous demonstrators while keeping delivery lightweight.
- Support for social exchange: small interpretive prompts and spatial micro-zones for discussion can reinforce peer-to-peer sharing without obstructing circulation.

These lessons were essential for refinements of future Parcours-based dissemination formats and touring scenarios.

Open Space Museum (Basel) – Exploratory Dissemination Feedback

In addition to the Parcour evaluation, an exploratory visitor survey was conducted during the Open Space Museum (OSM) installation at Uferstrasse in Basel. Due to the situational and experimental nature of the public-space deployment, the number of collected responses was limited; the survey is therefore considered qualitative and indicative rather than statistically representative. The collected feedback indicates that visitors perceived the OSM installation as accessible and engaging within a public-space context. Respondents highlighted the value of encountering cultural and research content outside traditional museum environments and reported positive interaction with the installation. Feedback further suggests that the OSM format supported spontaneous engagement and social interaction in public space, and that visitors expressed interest in encountering similar installations in other locations.

Lessons Learned (OSM Basel – Uferstrasse)

The Basel deployment confirmed the Open Space Museum (OSM) as a viable dissemination format in a public-space context, while highlighting several practical considerations for future installations:

- **Visibility and legibility:** in open environments, clear signage and a concise “what is this / how to engage” entry cue are essential to reduce hesitation and invite spontaneous participation.
- **Low-threshold engagement:** simple first actions (e.g., “look / sit / touch / listen”) help people enter the experience quickly and support a broad audience, including passers-by with limited time.
- **Social activation:** design features that encourage shared use (small gathering points, prompts for exchange, or cooperative elements) strengthen the OSM concept as a social dissemination format.
- **Context sensitivity:** the surrounding environment (noise, weather, circulation patterns, competing stimuli) strongly influences dwell time and should be considered in placement, timing, and the robustness of materials.
- **Iterative scaling:** small-scale deployments benefit from lightweight, repeatable modules that can be adapted to site constraints while preserving the core OSM logic.

These lessons will inform the refinement of future OSM deployments and support the transfer of the format to additional public settings.

2.1.3 SITEM (March 2025)

As participants in **SITEM 2025 (25–26 March 2025, Paris)**, the PERCEIVE consortium had the opportunity to showcase first preliminary results and engage with museum and cultural-sector stakeholders. The presentation focused on early demonstrators and tools that translate PERCEIVE research into public-facing formats and professional workflows.

Demonstrators and tools presented

- **The Scream Scaper Demonstrator:** explores colour perception beyond purely visual experience by translating colour variations in Edvard Munch’s *The Scream* into sound and

light. Two photographic captures are compared to generate a 3D topographical difference map that makes changes perceptible.

- **The Autochrome Demonstrator:** presents an approach to photo restoration and interpretation by separating the key material layers of autochromes—the coloured starch mosaic and the black-and-white panchromatic emulsion—into distinct physical layers that can be examined individually or recombined.
- **CoDesign Tool:** supports the design of engaging digital experiences for cultural heritage contexts by facilitating collaborative ideation through a structured yet adaptable methodology.
- **MuLaX tool:** a web-based 3D environment to visualise, inspect, manipulate, and compare analytical/colour data as layers directly on a 3D model of an artwork.

Communication and dissemination material

To amplify visibility around SITEM 2025, PERCEIVE contributed to a joint press release with the MuseIT project, distributed through both projects' websites and social media channels (link: [Press Communicate: MuseIT & PERCEIVE: Two Innovative European Projects at SITEM! - PERCEIVE](#)). The release announced the joint presence at SITEM (Carrousel du Louvre, Paris) and summarised the visitor-facing experiences presented at each stand: MuseIT (Stand IM10) showcased a multisensory virtual exhibition combining VR with the Skinetic haptic vest, aligned with the project's inclusion and accessibility agenda; PERCEIVE (Stand IM7) presented early results through demonstrators and collaborative design tools supporting the project's colour-preservation scenarios (e.g., Autochrome interpretation, lost polychromy diagnostics, multisensory translation of colour variations in *The Scream*, and collaborative ideation for museum applications). The press release positioned both projects within a shared objective of expanding access to cultural experiences through interactive technologies.

Figure 4: Excerpt of posts from the social media channel of the project showing PERCEIVE participation at SITEM

2.2 Scientific final events

In order to organise a final scientific event, the consortium started identifying the most appropriate solution during 2024, considering two possibilities: (1) a single event organised in several federated smaller conferences and workshop, spread out over several of the partner locations or (2) one main scientific event organized within a larger conference. Partners finally decided to give the priority to the organisation of workshops and panels during the world congress DigitalHeritage, organised in September 2025 and hosted by the University of Siena (Italy).

DigitalHeritage is a federated event of leading scientific meetings in information technology for heritage, such as VSMM, Eurographics GCH, UNESCO's Memory of the World, Arqueologica2.0, Archaeovirtual, Virtuale Switzerland, and special events from CAA, CIPA, Space2Place, ICOMOS ICIP, and multiple others together in one venue with a prestigious joint. The first three editions have been organised in Marseille (2014), Granada (2016) and San Francisco (2018). Its main characteristics were particularly suited to the PERCEIVE project, especially due to the possibility of organising a PERCEIVE workshop within the main scientific congress, and to showcase demonstrators and prototypes in the DigitalHeritage Expo area.

Moreover, DigitalHeritage World Congress has been also the ideal venue for the organisation of a Policy Roundtable.

For the organisation of the scientific events, the consortium appointed a scientific committee that was in charge of the program, call and publication. The timeline set for the organisation and then pursued was the following:

- Step 1. Scientific Committee appointed [M17]
- Step 2. Identification of the venue, of the format and of the publication policy [M20]
- Step 3. Definition of the Scientific Program [M21]

- Step 4. Call for Papers [M22]
- Step 5. Organisation of the Policy Roundtable [M24]
- Step 6. Scientific Event [M32]

2.3 Hybrid exhibitions

As anticipated, PERCEIVE has organised within a hybrid exhibitions program, four different public exhibits, in two museums and in a public space (for the Open Space Museum):

- 1) **Perceive Isis' Colours (Mann museum , Naples - Italy)**
- 2) **Fragile Colours (Trondheim University Museum, Trondheim - Norway)**
- 3) **Tiny Conservators (Munch Museum, Oslo – Norway)**
- 4) **Open Space Museum (Basel)**

The planning, supported by the CoDesign Tool (Deliverable 6.3), included several phases, listed below:

1. definition of the context and general goals of the exhibition:
 - a. target audience,
 - b. star assets (scenarios and case studies),
 - c. institutional goals,
 - d. cognitive and emotional goals for the audience (authenticity, care, participation)
2. identification of the venues and spaces
3. ideation phase #1 - brainstorming [from keywords to concepts]
4. ideation phase #2 - themes identification
5. ideation phase #3 - narrative frame of the exhibition and title of the exhibition
6. identification of technological demonstrators and their use in the physical environment and with the physical assets
7. design of the exhibition
8. design and prototyping of demonstrators
9. exhibition organisation
10. exhibition set-up and opening
11. testing and closing

The co-design activities defined the context, needs and requirements, constraints, and ideas.

Context and Goals

Target audience

- Citizens
- Schools and Teachers
- Experts
- Families
- Young audience (teenagers and young adults)

Star Assets: Themes, Scenarios and Case studies

Themes:

- History of colour
- Science of colour
- Colour Perception
- ICT rendering and artificial intelligence

Scenarios:

- **Lost polychromy in classical sculpture**

This scenario focuses on the polychromy of sculptures from classical antiquity. It addresses key questions such as how remaining traces of colour can be identified, why colours disappeared over time, and to what extent the original appearance of classical sculptures can be reconstructed and preserved. Within the Open Space Museum (OSM), this scenario presents examples of scientific colour reconstruction and rendering approaches, supporting visitors' understanding of the complexity of ancient polychromy. Particular attention is given to the semantic role of colour, the perceptual impact of shades and materiality, and the inherent uncertainty of reconstruction processes, which depend on fragmentary evidence, painting techniques, and conservation states that are difficult to intuit from today's largely colourless sculptures.

- **Colour degradation in paintings and works of art**

This scenario focuses on the polychromy of sculptures from classical antiquity. It addresses key questions such as how remaining traces of colour can be identified, why colours disappeared over time, and to what extent the original appearance of classical sculptures can be reconstructed and preserved. Within the Open Space Museum (OSM), this scenario presents examples of scientific colour reconstruction and rendering approaches, supporting visitors' understanding of the complexity of ancient polychromy. Particular attention is given to the semantic role of colour, the perceptual impact of shades and materiality, and the inherent uncertainty of reconstruction processes, which depend on fragmentary evidence, painting techniques, and conservation states that are difficult to intuit from today's largely colourless sculptures.

- **Colour fading and degradation of historical textiles: dress and tapestry**

Historical textiles reveal exceptional craftsmanship but are particularly vulnerable to fading, degradation, and corrosion caused by light exposure, environmental conditions, and material instability. This scenario explores scientific methods for analysing and reconstructing colour in textiles, highlighting the perceptual and cultural significance of colour loss in garments and tapestries. Presented within the OSM, this scenario enhances public access to textile collections—including archive-held objects—while communicating the preservation challenges faced by conservators and the broader implications of environmental factors on textile heritage.

- **Colour deterioration in historical photo and films: autochromes and Kodacolor**

The preservation of historical photographs and motion pictures presents shared challenges related to material deterioration, technological obsolescence, and environmental exposure, while also requiring medium-specific strategies. This scenario focuses on early colour processes such as autochromes and colour film materials. Within the OSM, original objects and reconstructions are presented alongside explanations of the scientific principles behind

colour simulation, rendering, and preservation, offering insight into both the visual outcomes and the underlying research processes.

- **Colour Use in Born Digital Art**

This scenario addresses contemporary artistic practices in which artworks are native to digital media, including digital painting, 3D computer-generated art, virtual and augmented reality, interactive installations, and AI-assisted (including generative) methods. A particular focus is placed on Augmented Reality (AR) art, which merges digital content with physical space and introduces specific challenges for long-term preservation, documentation, and accessibility. Within the broader Open Space Museum (OSM) framework, born-digital art is presented alongside the other PERCEIVE scenarios, while a dedicated VR experience developed by the IRRL Lab (HSLU) enables visitors to explore a virtual representation of the OSM setting and engage with selected AR artworks and their interactions with the physical structures.

Considered Case Studies during the co-design activities have been:

- The complex of Isis in Pompeii: coloured frescoes and statues (MANN and Pompeii)
- Colour analysis and reconstruction of the classical statuary type of Venus Anadyomene (MANN INV 111383; Venus Anadyomene, INV 6292; Venus Anadyomene from Pompeii, INV126248; Venus Anadyomene, INV 6298; Venus Anadyomene from the Iseum of Pompeii, INV 109608 Lovatelli Venus INV 109611)
- The gold of the Venus Bikini (MANN INV 152798)
- The Scream by Edvard Munch (MUNCH)
- Road in Provence 1933.1221: a watercolour on paper by Paul Cezanne (AIC)
- Color fading in the Kimono (V&A FE.422-1992)
- Victorian dress (V&A T.7-1926)
- 16th century purse and pincushion (V&A T.52-1954)
- 16th century burse (V&A T.40-1986)
- Selection of autochrome plates from the esteemed collection (V&A)
- Examples of kodacolor films
- “Crystal Coffin” AR artwork by the Chinese artist duo Lily & Honglei (2014)
- “Ecce Homo” AR artwork by Arthur Clay with artist Ingo Lie (2017)
- “Drone” by Will Pappenheimer (2015)
- “Dose” by Will Pappenheimer (2011)
- “A Space Art Gallery”, Arthur Clay (2023)
- Information Virus, Warren Armstrong (2010)

Institutional Goals (Perceive objectives and Museums Goals)

- **HERITAGE SCIENCE:** Make Heritage Science results accessible to the creative industry (including Computer Graphics, Exhibition Design, Light Design, and Games Design)
- **CONSERVATION AND EXHIBITION:** Enhance museum curatorial approaches by utilizing digital shared methodologies to study and safely exhibit collections with a focus on color.
- **RECONSTRUCTION AND PREDICTION:** Improve colour reconstruction and prediction methodology and workflow, interconnecting heritage science with digital technology including material rendering and artificial intelligence

- **CITIZENS ENGAGEMENT:** Widen the access and explore the use of coloured collections from history and the present day involving visitors and citizens inside and outside museums, improving their understanding and at the same time increasing their engagement with experiences that could be perceived as “authentic”.
- **REAPPROPRIATION:** European citizens’ re-appropriation of coloured collections, increasing awareness of their fragility and significance through the cultivation of a “sense of care.” This involves the creation of wonder, a sense of belonging, and emotional and empathic connection.

These institutional and cognitive-emotional goals are implemented through the Open Space Museum (OSM), conceived as a transversal exhibition and engagement framework supporting all PERCEIVE scenarios and objectives, both onsite and online.

Cognitive and Emotional Goals (authenticity, care and participation)

- **AUTHENTICITY:** Prior to the philosopher Hegel, the concept of 'authenticity' was associated with the idea of self-awareness and aligning one's actions with the aim of being perceived as honest and truthful by society. In the 60s, the concept evolved, thanks to Jasper (1960) who considered “authenticity” something that can touch a person’s deeper self, enduring, evolving, and changing together with the individual. The exhibition aims to craft visitor experiences that feel deeply meaningful fostering a personal connection that resonates with individuals close to the inner part of the self.

This approach will also take into account the other two pillars of the authenticity, which extend beyond the “self”: The Others (the social pillar) and the World (the environment or in general what is around us). Therefore, we will design specific user experiences (UX) that enable individuals to express themselves, discover their own meaning, and engage in reflection.

- **CARE:** One of the exhibition's objectives is to encourage visitors to develop or strengthen a sense of care for coloured collections, fostering an attitude that regards these collections as significant enough to evoke emotions and prompt action when the objects are at risk or in need. Research on the 'care theory,' spanning philosophical, literary, historical-artistic, psychological, and neuroscience disciplines, offers insights into the caring process, which is generally understood to evolve through four phases: 'caring about,' 'taking care of,' 'care-giving,' and 'care-receiving.' This theory predominantly emphasizes the aspect of 'responsibility. The Caring Attitude refers to a deliberate and action-oriented event that occurs between two actors, where one needs help and protection and the other provides whatever they need. One of the main concepts around which this goal will be reached is through the development of metaphors where the fragility of the coloured collection will be perceived in an embodied way.
- **PARTICIPATION:** One of the primary objectives of the exhibition is to foster a deeper and more meaningful engagement with art and culture within the local community. This goal goes beyond the conventional notion of passive viewership and seeks to actively involve individuals in cultural experiences and events. To achieve this, the concept of an 'Open Space Museum' (OSM) has been conceived. In the context of the Open Space Museum (OSM), visitors assume an interactive role rather than passive spectators in their cultural exploration. This progressive approach encompasses a range of interactive and immersive installations, all designed to encourage tactile engagement and even personal artistic expression. Moreover, it

is crucial to emphasize that the OSM's influence extends beyond its physical boundaries. The OSM extends its presence into the digital domain, offering virtual encounters and online resources that facilitate participation in cultural activities for a global audience. By dismantling traditional barriers, promoting active involvement, and embracing both the physical and digital dimensions, the Open Space Museum represents a significant departure from conventional paradigms of art and culture engagement within communities. It serves as a multifaceted platform that transcends the confines of traditional museums, ushering in a new era marked by heightened accessibility and inclusivity in the realm of cultural experiences.

2.3.1 The Venues

The PERCEIVE partners identified and assessed potential venues capable of supporting high-visibility dissemination activities aligned with the project's objectives and scenarios. Two museums with strong relevance to colour research, conservation, and public engagement were initially selected as potential host venues: the **MUNCH** in Oslo and the **National Archaeological Museum of Naples (MANN)**.

B1. Naples and the MANN Museum

The **National Archaeological Museum of Naples (MANN)** was initially identified as a strategically relevant venue due to its internationally significant collections of classical sculpture, wall paintings, mosaics, and archaeological artefacts, which directly align with PERCEIVE's scenarios on lost polychromy and colour degradation in ancient materials. MANN's long-standing expertise in the scientific study, conservation, and communication of coloured archaeological heritage, combined with its capacity to host high-visibility public programmes, makes it a suitable venue for PERCEIVE dissemination activities. Dissemination initiatives hosted at MANN would enable PERCEIVE to reach both specialist and general audiences, raising awareness of colour preservation challenges while showcasing the project's methodologies, tools, and results. Nonetheless, as better explained in the following section (see [3.2.1.1 PERCEIVE Isis' Colours at MANN MUSEUM](#)) the venue was discarded and the exhibition relocated.

Figure 9: Wall painting on the East side of the portico, depicting Arpocrate

Figure 13: Images of the Anadyomene Venuses described below

B2. Oslo – MUNCH Museum

The MUNCH Museum in Oslo was identified as a strategically relevant venue due to its internationally recognised collection of modern artworks and its long-standing engagement in heritage science and conservation research. In particular, the museum's collection includes multiple versions of *The Scream* by **Edvard Munch**, which have been extensively studied in relation to colour instability, material degradation, and exhibition strategies. The museum's expertise in colour changes phenomena in modern painting, combined with its experience in communicating conservation research to the public through digital and interactive formats, makes MUNCH a highly suitable venue for PERCEIVE dissemination activities. Hosting PERCEIVE-related events or exhibitions at MUNCH would enable the project to reach a broad international audience while directly supporting dissemination around colour degradation, reconstruction, and preservation scenarios.

B3. Trondheim – University Museum

In collaboration with the Victoria and Albert Museum (V&A), Colourlab at NTNU, Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts (HSLU), Fraunhofer Institute for Computer Graphics Research (IGD), and the PERCEIVE project, PERCEIVE has organised the exhibition "Fragile Colours: Perceiving and Experiencing the Autochrome", open in November 2025. The exhibition explores autochromes delicate photographs through both physical and digital experiences. Visitors are invited to reflect on how we perceive, exhibit, and access fragile cultural heritage — and to discover how new technologies can bring lost colours back to life. As part of the PERCEIVE Horizon Europe project, researchers have studied the unique materiality and ageing of autochromes, developing digital methods for restoration and virtual exhibition. In the exhibition different tools and project outputs have been integrated and included: 1) LDE tool / autochrome box, 2) DeGreening Tool / Interactive screen, 3) Perceive methodology, 4) Autochrome Demonstrator.

Link. <https://www.ntnu.edu/museum/fragile-colours>; <https://perceive-horizon.eu/index.php/2025/11/07/fragile-colours-perceiving-and-experiencing-the-autochrome/>

B4. The Spaces Outside the Museums

In addition to museum-based dissemination activities, PERCEIVE implemented dissemination actions in public spaces through the Open Space Museum (OSM), a mobile and modular exhibition framework designed for deployment outside traditional museum contexts. Public-space installations enable the project to engage audiences who may not actively seek museum experiences, thereby broadening access and visibility.

During the reporting period, the Open Space Museum was presented in **Uferstrasse**, where it functioned as a hybrid dissemination platform combining physical structures with digital content accessible via personal devices. The installation was designed to operate autonomously in open environments, complying with local regulations and without the need for external power supply or the presence of original artworks.

The OSM's modular design, low security requirements, and adaptability to diverse urban contexts make it a suitable dissemination format for presenting PERCEIVE concepts, tools, and scenarios in

public space. This approach supports citizen engagement and participation while extending PERCEIVE dissemination beyond institutional settings.

Dissemination in public space was supported by modular physical elements serving as mediation supports, combined with digital applications that enabled visitors to access interpretative content, explore PERCEIVE scenarios, and engage with project themes. This approach allowed PERCEIVE to communicate research concepts related to colour preservation, perception, and authenticity in a non-institutional setting, fostering citizen engagement and participation beyond museum environments.

B4. Complementarity and Synergies Across Dissemination Venues

Taken together, the selected dissemination venues—museum-based contexts (MUNCH and MANN) and public-space deployment through the Open Space Museum (OSM)—form a complementary ecosystem that supports the dissemination of PERCEIVE research outcomes across diverse audiences and settings. Each venue contributes distinct strengths while addressing different facets of the project’s scenarios and objectives. Museum environments such as MUNCH and MANN provide authoritative institutional contexts in which PERCEIVE results related to colour degradation, reconstruction, and preservation can be disseminated to specialist audiences, cultural professionals, and the general public. These venues enable direct engagement with disciplinary expertise, conservation practice, and established visitor flows, reinforcing the scientific credibility and relevance of the project’s outcomes. In parallel, dissemination in public space through the Open Space Museum extends PERCEIVE’s reach beyond institutional boundaries, engaging citizens who may not actively seek museum experiences. By operating in open urban contexts and combining physical structures with digital mediation, the OSM supports participation, accessibility, and informal learning, while communicating PERCEIVE concepts in a lightweight and adaptable format. Together, these dissemination contexts create synergies between research, experimentation, and public engagement. They allow PERCEIVE to articulate its results across multiple scales—from controlled museum settings to open public environments—thereby strengthening the visibility, accessibility, and societal impact of the project’s research outputs.

3 PERCEIVE Final Scientific Events

From the outset, PERCEIVE adopted a cluster approach to scientific dissemination, replacing a single large stand-alone final event with a coordinated set of smaller, partner-embedded activities, including workshops, demonstrator showcases, and conference contributions. This strategy ensured continuous visibility and sustained engagement with stakeholders across diverse contexts, while also providing a high-profile international focal point through PERCEIVE’s integration into the Digital Heritage World Congress (DH25), hosted by the University of Siena (Italy) in September 2025.

3.1 PERCEIVE Scientific Event: Digital Heritage 2025

The **Digital Heritage International Congress 2025**, held in Siena from September 8 to 12, served as a premier global forum for the intersection of advanced technology and cultural preservation. Bringing together an international community of researchers, museum curators, and creative technologists, the event addressed the evolving challenges of documenting and communicating heritage in the digital age. Within this high-profile context, the **PERCEIVE** project played a central

role, presenting three years of interdisciplinary research focused on the study and communication of "coloured" collections through artificial intelligence and virtual experiences.

During the congress, a major thematic session was held to present the scientific and theoretical outputs of the project: **"Exhibiting the Unexhibitable" (T8, S1)**, moderated and chaired by Catlin Langford (Victoria and Albert Museum) and Donata Magrini (CNR ISPC). This session presented the project's broad research scope, which encompasses five diverse scenarios: lost polychromy in ancient sculptures, fading colours in paintings and works on paper, textiles, historical photo and film collections, and digital-born art. Several key papers described methodologies and results that push beyond the current state of the art:

- **Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Coloured Collections through AI and Virtual Experiences**
Sofia Pescarin*; Birgitte Aga; Yoko Arteaga; Cristiana Barandoni; Federica Bonifazi; Beatrice Boracchi; Lucia Burgio; Ivana Cerato; Irina Ciortan; Arthur Clay; Bruno Fanini; Chiara Gemma Fedon; Daniele Ferdani; Holger Graf; Jon Hardeberg; Donata Magrini; Marcello Massidda; Paschalis Panteleris; Giorgos Papadopoulos; Marios Pitikakis; Irina Crina Anca Sandu; Saptarshi Neil Sinha; Panagiotis Siozos; Sophia Sotiropoulou; Samuele Spotti; Petros Stavroulakis; Laura Travaglini; Giorgio Trumpy; Manuele Veggi
An introductory paper detailed PERCEIVE's dedication to the analysis, interpretation, reconstruction, and conservation of colours across various historical scenarios.
- **An Atlas-based Approach for Appearance-aware Virtual 3D Restoration and Simulation of Fading in Fugitive Textiles**
Saptarshi Neil Sinha*; Irina Ciortan; Tom Kneiphof; Paul Julius Kühn; Brenda Doherty; Lucia Burgio; Richard Palmer; Catarina Pinto; Laura Martel; David Buti; Letizia Monico; Reinhard Klein; Arjan Kuijper; Michael Weinmann
Research presented an atlas-based approach for the virtual 3D restoration of fugitive textiles at the Victoria and Albert Museum. This method utilizes textile mockups and accelerated aging to simulate and render colour fading.
- **Interactive and immersive discovery of diagnostic processes on multi-layered 3D collections on the web: the MuLaX tool**
Bruno Fanini*; Marcello Massidda; Daniele Ferdani; Federica Bonifazi; Donata Magrini; Roberta Iannaccone; Cristiana Barandoni
This paper introduced "MuLaX," a Web3D tool developed to offer interactive and immersive discovery of diagnostic processes. It allows users to examine multi-layered 3D collections and scientific analytical data online.
- **Text2Autochrome: Text guided autochrome synthesis using generative models**
Paul Julius Kühn*; Saptarshi Neil Sinha; Duc Anh Nguyen; Robin Horst; Arjan Kuijper; Dieter Fellner
The "Text2Autochrome" study demonstrated the use of generative AI and Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) to synthesize digitized autochromes from text prompts, preserving original color filter effects and granularity.
- **What can a historic black and white photograph tell us about the original colours of a painting? A case study on Edvard Munch's the Scream 1910(?)**
Panagiotis Siozos; Irina Crina Anca Sandu; Petros Ioannis Stavroulakis; Sophia Sotiropoulou
A computational case study on Edvard Munch's *The Scream* (1910?) illustrated how historical black-and-white photographs can be combined with modern hyperspectral imaging to detect color changes in artworks over time.
- **Implementing Curiosity Hooks and Caring Practices in the Reconstruction of Lost Polychromy: Design Prototypes for Interactive Experiences.**
Federica Bonifazi; Manuele Veggi; Marcello Massidda; Daniele Ferdani; Sofia Pescarin
Designing authentic digital experiences
Samuele Spotti; Federica Bonifazi; Laura Travaglini; Marcello Massidda; Sofia Pescarin
Two papers focused on the visitor experience: one explored implementing "curiosity hooks" and "caring practices" in the reconstruction of lost polychromy, while the other operationalized an authenticity framework structured around the dimensions of "Self, Others, and World" to design actionable strategies for digital and XR experiences.

In parallel with the thematic sessions, the project maintained a significant presence at **Booth 5b** in the **DH25 Expo** area. This space served as a primary location for showcasing PERCEIVE's tools and resources through ad hoc sessions and special events designed to provide live demonstrations of their functionalities. These demonstrations featured **MuLaX-AVS**, which enables users to interact with scientific data overlaid on 3D models, and the **Co-Design Tool**, a card-game-based framework for designing hybrid interactive experiences. Other showcased resources included **StyleShade3D** for AI-assisted semantic stylization of 3D models, the **Light Damage Estimator** for visualizing light exposure risks, and **SimTex** for the 3D visualization of colour changes in textiles.

Figure 17: PERCEIVE boot 5a at Digital Heritage 2025

Moreover, booth 5a hosted PERCEIVE Science Demonstrators showing how the model of the traditional museum or gallery visit can be transformed into an adventurous exploration, making the act of viewing and interacting with artwork a significant new experience. The booth featured a set of demonstrators that showcase ongoing research and the intricate technologies driving the PERCEIVE project, particularly its advancements in relation to the Open Space Museum prototype.

Lastly, booth 21 hosted the PERCEIVE Isis' Colours exhibition, described in detail in paragraph [3.2.1.2 PERCEIVE Isis' Colours at Digital Heritage 2025](#).

To maximize visibility, an extensive multi-channel outreach strategy was implemented, coordinating efforts across the official project website and major social media platforms. The strategy focused on providing comprehensive access to scientific results through the publication of detailed research articles and case study summaries. Digital communication was tightly integrated with the congress activities by providing live updates and real-time coverage of the thematic sessions and booth interactions, both on the project socials and website and the conference communication channels.

3.2 PERCEIVE Hybrid Exhibition

3.2.1 PERCEIVE Isis' Colours

3.2.1.1 PERCEIVE Isis' Colours at MANN MUSEUM (Exhibition concept not implemented on site)

As part of the planning of the hybrid exhibition, the MANN Museum (Naples) proposed a set of exhibition rooms to host a temporary PERCEIVE exhibition, as mentioned above. However, due to unforeseen logistical issues, the MANN venue could not ultimately be used to host the PERCEIVE Isis' Colours exhibition. It was therefore decided to relocate the entire exhibition to the Digital Heritage 2025 Expo in Siena (see next Section).

Although the exhibition did not take place at the MANN as originally planned, the initial spatial configuration developed for the museum is documented here. These design schemes informed curatorial routing, technical feasibility assessments, and the overall exhibition concept, and they represent a substantial body of design work carried out by the partners. Owing to its scalable and

modular nature, the original exhibition design was successfully adapted to the new venue, confirming the flexibility, scalability, and adaptability of the PERCEIVE prototypes developed for the event.

The essential information reported below is therefore intended to illustrate the original exhibition plan developed for the MANN venue.

Planned Location

MANN Museum, rooms 90-92

Planned Period

November-December 2025

Exhibition Concept

The original exhibition concept was structured as a sequential visitor journey articulated across three main spaces, designed to progressively introduce the project themes and the WP6 prototypes.

Figure XX. Draft 3D simulation of the exhibition

The exhibition opened with a **Welcome Room**, conceived as an introductory space framing both the cultural context of the cult of Isis and the overarching objectives of the PERCEIVE project. This room introduced visitors to the theme of lost polychromy and to the exhibition narrative through an emotionally driven video, explicitly addressing the sense of loss associated with vanished colours and fragmented heritage. Informational panels and digital links provided further contextualisation and connections with the museum's permanent collections.

The second space was dedicated to the **Caring prototype**. This room focused on revealing the scientific process behind the rediscovery of lost polychromy, highlighting the complexity, uncertainty, and care involved in heritage analysis and conservation. Through a combination of museum objects, information panels, projections, and tangible interactive modules, visitors were invited to explore diagnostic techniques, analytical methods, and interpretative steps, fostering a reflective and informed approach to heritage investigation.

The third and final space was devoted to the **Authenticity prototype**. This environment presented a hypothetical reconstruction of the Isis temple, enhanced by a collaborative and role-based experience. By selecting different roles (e.g. priest, worshipper, painter), visitors could engage with multiple interpretative perspectives, exploring how authenticity is negotiated through reconstruction choices and participatory interaction.

For all the exhibition spaces and installations described above, detailed exhibition designs and three-dimensional simulations were developed in order to support the on-site implementation of the prototypes. These materials included spatial layouts, installation schemes, and visualisations intended to simulate the final exhibition setup. However, the design phase did not progress to physical implementation at the MANN venue, and the project activities related to this exhibition therefore concluded at the design and simulation stage.

Although the exhibition was not implemented at the MANN as originally planned, the tripartite spatial structure described above was maintained, as documented in the following sections. The main exhibition components and design logics were further developed into modular, transportable, and self-standing elements, enabling flexible spatial configurations independent of the host venue. This design strategy supports scalability and reuse in different institutional and exhibition contexts, while also allowing for the potential reinstallation of the exhibition at the MANN in the future, should appropriate conditions be met, even beyond the duration of the PERCEIVE project. From a technical and design perspective, this approach ensures the robustness, sustainability, and long-term applicability of the exhibition framework developed within WP6.

Figure XX First version of the exhibition layouts of the Caring room designed for the exhibition planned at the MANN Museum

Figure XX: “Different version of the exhibition layouts and simulations of the Authenticity room designed for the exhibition planned at the MANN Museum

In the context of the final event at DH25, both the Caring and Authenticity prototypes were implemented and presented in their definitive versions, entitled “**Echoes of Loss**” and “**The Gifts of Isis.**” For the descriptive aspects related to the three installations across the exhibition spaces, reference should be made to the following section describing the DH25 implementation, as the exhibition contents and narrative structure remain unchanged. Technical details concerning system functionality and interaction design are documented in Deliverable 6.1.

In addition to the indoor exhibition spaces, the exhibition design also envisaged the deployment of selected **Open Space Museum (OSM)**. This external installation was conceived as an extension of the exhibition experience, allowing the presentation of OSM modules in a self-standing and modular configuration.

The OSM was initially conceived for the MANN museum context as an atrium-based installation positioned in the museum’s entry zone. In this configuration, the OSM was designed as a pass-through dissemination format that visitors would encounter while moving through the entrance area, enabling lightweight, modular engagement without requiring a dedicated temporary-exhibition route. This placement strategy aimed to maximise visibility and accessibility by integrating PERCEIVE content into an everyday circulation space, supporting brief encounters as well as longer moments of interaction depending on visitor interest.

Following the change in the MANN exhibition pathway, the OSM design team developed Transforms as alternative, scenario-focused configurations of the Open Space Museum to preserve dissemination capacity under different spatial and hosting constraints. Alongside the different sizes of the Open Space Museum, which can bring together all five scenarios (Painting, Photography, Textiles, Sculpture, and Digital Art), two alternative versions were developed as Transforms. Unlike the full Open Space Museum, which showcases the complete spectrum of experiences, Transforms

concentrate on one or more selected scenarios. The idea behind Transforms is to ensure flexibility and adaptability, making it possible to present a more focused selection of experiences in contexts where space, time, or audience needs call for a scaled-down version. In this way, Transforms extend the reach of the Open Space Museum by offering smaller, curated exhibitions that still carry forward its core themes and engagement logic.

Two Transform configurations were prepared for the MANN context: (1) “Goddesses and Their Lovers”, planned for the museum’s outdoor garden area, and (2) “The Isis Reflectorium”, planned for an indoor museum setting. Both Transforms were conceived as scaled variants of the OSM, enabling a targeted presentation of PERCEIVE content while retaining the OSM’s core engagement logic and modular structure.

Figure XX. Museum’s outdoor garden area planned to host “Goddesses and Their Lovers”.

Transform 1: Goddesses and Their Lovers

Goddesses and Their Lovers is a site-responsive installation conceived as a myth-inspired garden of reflection and repose. At its core is a series of hammock stations—five arranged in symbolic pairs and one solitary—evoking relationships drawn from Greco-Roman and Egyptian mythology (divine unions, mortal encounters, and acts of self-love and transformation). Visitors are invited to physically inhabit these roles by reclining in the hammocks, translating symbolic narratives into a bodily, participatory experience. The installation also integrates Born Digital Art through mobile-accessible augmented reality layers, bridging mythic archetypes with contemporary digital storytelling.

Transform 2: The Isis Reflectorium

The Isis Reflectorium reimagines ritual architecture as a contemporary environment of play, myth, and reflection, inspired by the ancient Iseum at Pompeii. The visitor experience is structured through contrasting elements - objects and images that shift between archaeological “absence” and reconstructed colour presence - and participatory actions that transform play into a collective, ritual-like logic. The configuration is articulated through five symbolic parts echoing Iseum architecture: The Tower, The Oracle, The Court, The Mirror, and The Cage, together framing participation, transformation, and self-reflection within a coherent spatial sequence.

In this case as well this case, the OSM was not implemented at the MANN as originally planned. However, *transform 1* was subsequently presented in Zürich at the AQUARIUM Galerie (Max-Frisch-Bad Letzigraben) as part of the exhibition “A Ticket to the Moon”. The public programme included an opening performance on 14 September 2025 and additional public events during November and December 2025, concluding with a Finissage on 14 December 2025. *Transform 2* is planned to be presented at Manifattura Tabacchi (Florence) and integrated into the Final Review meeting on 2 March as a deliberately reduced, yet conceptually complete demonstrator configuration.

3.2.1.2 PERCEIVE Isis' Colours at Digital Heritage 2025

Location

The PERCEIVE Isis Colours originally conceived for the MANN Museum was therefore adapted and implemented at the Digital Heritage 2025 International Congress & Expo in Siena, Italy. Following its

presentation at the congress, the exhibition was subsequently relocated to Manifattura Tabacchi in Florence, where it remains accessible to the public during scheduled events.

Period

In occasion of the *Digital Heritage 2025* in Siena the exhibition took place from **September 8 to September 12, 2025**. This five-day period allowed international congress attendees and the general public to engage with the project's research through interactive prototypes and multisensory installations.

About the exhibition

The exhibition "Perceive Isis' Colours" addresses the critical issue of lost polychromy in classical antiquity, specifically targeting the fragile and often misrepresented history of colour in ancient art. Developed through a collaboration between the National Archaeological Museum of Naples (MANN) and the CNR Institute of Heritage Science (ISPC), the exhibition serves as a tangible application of the caring and authenticity prototype PERCEIVE project.

MANN played a key role in the dissemination and demonstrator activities of the PERCEIVE project, providing a substantial contribution to the scientific and documentary content required for the development of publications, prototypes, and exhibitions. As a cultural institution partner, the museum made available artworks, archival documentation, historical drawings, photographs, essential for defining and contextualising the case study on the Temple of Isis in Pompeii and its polychrome collections preserved at the Museum. This contribution constituted the material basis for the content embedded in the PERCEIVE Isis' Colours exhibition, with the production of content through three main actions:

1. Selection and provision of museum materials (objects, archival sources, photographic documentation, historical data);
2. Scientific support and curatorial validation, ensuring archaeological, historical, and museological accuracy of the narrative and interpretive choices;
3. Co-design of curatorial narratives and exhibition contexts, in collaboration with CNR ISPC and the project's scientific partners.

This form of involvement enabled the definition of a scientifically relevant and museographically coherent case study, characterised by exceptional historical documentation and by a set of polychrome artworks preserved within the museum. The Temple of Isis case study aligned with research questions related to authenticity, care, and colour perception, offering a real-world context for investigating the fragility of ancient polychromy, conservation practices, and the challenges of digital reconstruction. Within the exhibition domain, MANN contributed to the curatorial design of the "Perceive Isis' Colours" exhibition presented at Digital Heritage 2025 in Siena, providing content, artefacts, and curatorial expertise for the construction of the narrative spaces and multimedia installations. The exhibition is divided into two thematic sections, reflecting two of the prototypes developed within WP6: the caring prototype, "Echoes of Loss", and the Authenticity prototype, "The Gifts of Isis" (see Del. 6.1, sec. 4.1). While the first section focuses on fostering a caring attitude towards fragile collections and specifically towards lost polychromy of roman statues, the second section is aimed at conveying an authentic experiential approach, taking into account both classical polychromy and fragile Pompeiian frescoes.

The two sections were anticipated by a **welcome area** where visitors were provided with an overview of the PERCEIVE project and its objectives before they entered the exhibition. This area was also essential for user research, offering a seated space where participants could easily and comfortably complete evaluation forms before and after their experience (for full details on the evaluation process, see Del. 7.2).

Echoes of Loss: This section highlights the beauty and fragility of ancient colour, guiding visitors through the diagnostic and reconstructive processes used to recover faded pigments. It begins with an emotional video narrative that explores the splendour of the sanctuary's original colours and the subsequent tragedy of their loss following the eruption of Vesuvius. Visitors then enter the "Colour Lab", an investigative workshop where they follow the path of the research process behind the reconstruction of lost polychromy, starting from the study of literary, iconographic and archaeological sources. They are then led to interact with a 3D-printed replica of the Venus Anadyomene, case of study currently in permanent exhibition at the MANN (National Archaeological Museum of Naples). Using interactive replicas of scientific instruments, such as microscopes, spectrometers and a flashlight to simulate imaging techniques, participants simulate diagnostic analysis to reveal microscopic pigment traces. The journey concludes with "Echoes of Colours", an interactive projection mapping where visitors physically "lift" objects of increasing weight to reveal hypothetical colour reconstructions, emphasizing that the recovery of the past is a careful negotiation between evidence and interpretation and will never reach a definitive unique hypothesis of reconstruction.

Figure 18: "Echoes of Loss" section of the exhibition : a) Introductory video b) ColourLab interactive installation c) Echoes of Colours projection

The Gifts of Isis: This second application consists of a multiplayer, multisensory interactive prototype that engages groups of three visitors in a collaborative "authentic" journey. The experience uses game mechanics and a layered narrative where participants initially choose a symbolic gift (Wisdom, Creativity, or Patience) to be assigned historical roles like Architect, Painter, or Sculptor. After completing digital tasks related to these crafts, such as reassembling frescoes or identifying architectural plans, the characters undergo a metamorphosis into ritual figures (Priestess, Musician, Devotee). The interaction then shifts from digital devices to physical space, requiring visitors to collaborate through touch (selecting linen robes), smell (identifying sacred perfumes like Kyphi), and hearing (recognizing the sound of the sistrum). This collaborative ritual aims to activate all the dimensions identified in the theoretical framework of authenticity, stimulating the Self, Others, and the World to produce a shared sense of authenticity.

Figure 19: Set up of "The Gifts of Isis" installation with visitors playing

Promotion and Digital Outreach To maximize visibility, an extensive promotional campaign was conducted via social media platforms (LinkedIn, Facebook and Instagram) and the official PERCEIVE website to sponsor the event. The digital strategy focused on showcasing the prototype development through backstage images teasers and storytelling, explaining how digital interfaces were merged with diagnostic analyses and used to bridge the gap between fragmented remains and public engagement. This outreach ensured the exhibition's scientific goals reached an international audience beyond the physical attendees in Siena.

The outreach was further consolidated through a series of coordinated digital publications:

- **Official Website and Newsletter:** A description of the exhibition and a digital version of the catalogue were made available on the [PERCEIVE project website](#), serving as a central repository for research data and exhibition highlights and insights were shared on the September Newsletter of the project ([here](#)).
- **Social Media:** Text and media were shared primarily on Facebook and LinkedIn fostering a real-time dialogue with the global Digital Heritage community, showing behind the scenes of the development of the prototype (see an example [here](#)), the theory behind the design (example for the caring prototype [here](#) and for the authenticity [here](#)) and lastly of the setting up and installation on the days of exhibition ([here](#)).

Participation

The exhibition reached a total of a couple of hundred participants throughout the Digital Heritage 2025 Congress. While the "The Gifts of Isis" prototype was intentionally designed for structured sessions involving groups of three visitors to maintain the high-quality, multisensory interaction required for a collaborative experience, the overall flow of the exhibition remained continuous and steady. This was made possible by the layout of the space, which allowed for a constant stream of engagement in the "Echoes of Loss" section. A significant portion of the participants consisted of museum directors, heritage scientists, and digital curators who attended the Siena Congress. Their participation fostered critical discussions on how these prototypes could be implemented across other European cultural institutions.

Nonetheless, the reach of the exhibition extended beyond registered congress attendees. Since the Expo was open to the public freely and without cost, the installations attracted a significant number of external visitors, including local residents, students, and tourists. This open-access format facilitated a diverse demographic of participants, allowing the project's research on authenticity and heritage care to be experienced by a broader audience.

3.2.1.3 PERCEIVE Isis' Colours at ArcheoVirtual2025

The project's outreach and dissemination efforts culminated in its participation at **Archeovirtual**, the multimedia exhibition held during the **Borsa Mediterranea del Turismo Archeologico (BMTA) 2025**. The event took place at the **NEXT - New Exhibition Former SAIM Tobacco Factory** in Capaccio Paestum (SA), Italy, from October 30 to November 2, 2025.

A dedicated booth within the exhibition area was specifically outfitted to host the "**Echoes of Loss**" caring prototype. This installation allowed a broad audience of cultural heritage professionals, students, and tourists to engage directly with the scientific and emotional journey of recovering the lost polychromy of the Temple of Isis.

The significance of the installation was highlighted by the Italian national broadcasting service, **RaiNews**, which featured a dedicated video report titled "*Il colore perduto: il recupero della policromia al BMTA 2025 di Paestum*" (October 30, 2025). The coverage included a guided walkthrough of the prototype demonstrating to a nationwide audience how the PERCEIVE project integrates advanced diagnostic studies with interactive storytelling to bridge the gap between archaeological research and public interaction.

Figure 20: Set up of "Echoes of Loss" at ArcheoVirtual 2025 in Paestum

3.2.1.4 PERCEIVE Isis' Colours at Manifattura Tabacchi (Florence)

Following its successful presentation at international congresses and exhibitions, the exhibition has now been permanently relocated to **Manifattura Tabacchi** in Florence. It is currently hosted within the **E-RIHS (European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science)** facilities, where the setup remains available to the public and stakeholders during special events and institutional openings. This location serves as a living laboratory for the project's legacy, allowing for continued testing and demonstration of the hybrid prototypes in a professional heritage science environment.

3.2.1.5 Next events in planning

Looking forward, the project's dissemination activities will continue with its presence at **TourismA 2026**, the International Exhibition of Archaeology and Cultural Tourism, held in Florence at the end of February. On this occasion, the "**The Gifts of Isis**" authenticity prototype will be hosted in one of the booths of the exhibition area, providing a new opportunity for the general public and tourism professionals to experience the multisensory reconstruction of the Temple of Isis. This participation underscores the project's commitment to long-term impact and its ability to adapt complex scientific research for major public-facing cultural events.

3.2.2 PERCEIVE Tiny Conservators

Tiny Conservators is an interactive **caring prototype** developed by the MUNCH Museum as part of the PERCEIVE project. Its primary aim is not only to communicate the science of colour change in artworks, but to cultivate a culture of care among children and families.

The experience is anchored in a colour-change case study focusing on Edvard Munch's *The Scream* ('1910 ?' version), a painting whose pigments—particularly in the sky—are highly vulnerable to degradation caused by light, humidity, and time. Rather than presenting conservation research through text-based explanation, the installation translates material fragility into a cooperative and playful scenario.

Players take on the role of "Tiny Conservators", imagined as guardians living inside the microscopic layers of the painting. Their task is to protect colour from three antagonistic forces—Time, Humidity, and Light—represented as flamboyant, personified threats within the game world. Through this narrative framing, conservation becomes an active and shared responsibility rather than an abstract concept.

Figure 21: Children engaging and playing *Tiny Conservators* in the Amfi at MUNCH

Location and Period

Tiny Conservators was presented as a live public prototype at the MUNCH Museum in Oslo, located in *The Amfi*, the museum's circular, glass-walled lobby space. The Amfi is a non-ticketed, highly visible public area that functions as a social threshold between exhibition spaces and visitor circulation, allowing both active participation and spectatorship.

The installation was open to the public from 5 December to 29 December 2025, during the museum's regular opening hours: 10:00–18:00 on Monday, Tuesday, and Sunday, and 10:00–21:00 on Wednesday through Saturday. Throughout this period, the installation was available continuously from opening until closing time and was advertised on the MUNCH Museum website as part of the public programme.

Figure 22: Photo of the Amfi space at MUNCH by Einar Aslaksen

Exhibition Overview and PERCEIVE Context

Gameplay, Care, and Cooperation

Gameplay is designed as a cooperative experience, supporting between one and six players simultaneously. Children must coordinate their actions to protect pigment health, shield each other's avatars, and respond collectively to environmental threats. Care is enacted not only towards the artwork but also towards fellow players, reinforcing empathy, collaboration, and shared responsibility as core values.

Figure 23: Game interface visualising cumulative colour damage on the surface of *The Scream*, with areas affected by light exposure highlighted and conservation failure indicated.

Figure 24: Cooperative gameplay in *Tiny Conservators*, where children work together to protect pigment health and support each other's actions.

Figure 25: Encounter with the Royal Elementals—Time, Humidity, and Light—personified as environmental threats to the stability of colour in the painting.

Figure 26: Players coordinating strategies to counteract environmental forces, illustrating shared responsibility and collaborative care for the artwork.

Figure 27: Final boss encounter with the Lady of Light, staged directly on the painted surface of *The Scream*, symbolising the extreme vulnerability of colour to light damage.

Physical Installation and Interaction Design

The installation transformed The Amfi into an immersive, participatory conservation arena. Large-scale projections animated the digital game world across the curved surfaces of the space, while responsive coloured lighting reacted dynamically to in-game events such as pigment damage or recovery. Surround sound amplified the presence of the antagonistic forces, extending the narrative beyond the screen and into the physical environment.

Figure 28: The Amfi space at MUNCH during live operation of Tiny Conservators.

At the centre of the installation were six tactile game stations, referred to as ‘conservosauruses’. These physical interfaces were designed to be robust, child-friendly, and inclusive, with simplified controls and ergonomic forms adapted for young players and varied abilities. The conservosauruses anchored the digital experience in bodily interaction, making conservation tangible, touchable, and spatially shared. The room accommodated approximately 50 audience members at a time, including active players, waiting participants, carers, and observers. The circular layout ensured that play remained visible from all sides, turning individual play sessions into a collective and social experience.

Figure 29: Detail of a conservosaur controller with embedded lights and sensors.

Figure 30: Overview of *The Amfi* transformed into the *Tiny Conservators* installation. The room's immersive lighting and textile elements create a tactile, sensory environment that extends the digital game into physical space.

Participation and Estimated Audience

Each gameplay session lasted approximately 5–20 minutes, with observations indicating that shorter play sessions predominated during peak hours. While six conservosaur stations were installed, observations indicate that four stations were in consistent use throughout most opening hours. During busy periods—especially afternoons, weekends, and peak holiday days—queues frequently formed outside *The Amfi*.

Considering near-continuous use of four game stations across approximately 242 public opening hours and adjusting for shorter average session lengths during peak periods, the number of direct participants is estimated at around 3,500 players over the exhibition period.

This corresponds to an average of approximately 140–240 players per day, a figure considered realistic when compared with other high-traffic interactive installations at *MUNCH*. In addition to active players, a substantially larger number of visitors encountered the installation as observers, including family members, carers, and passers-by.

This layered participation contributed to a shared atmosphere of collective play, attention, and care within the lobby space. To support interpretation beyond gameplay, a mediation booklet was produced in Norwegian and English and distributed free of charge in *The Amfi*. The booklet introduced the game scenario, explained colour change and conservation themes, and connected the playful experience to the wider aims of the *PERCEIVE* project.

Figure 31: Mediation booklet for Tiny Conservators (Norwegian and English editions). The free booklet introduces the game scenario, explains colour change and conservation themes, and situates the installation within the PERCEIVE project.

<p>TINY CONSERVATOR & CONSERVE-O-SAURUS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tap the button to fly up! Gravity will do the rest and take you back down. Time your taps carefully. 2. Use the arcade stick to glide left and right like a colour-saving hero. 	<p>BATTLING THE MINIONS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Bump them from above to knock them silly! 2. Chomp them up by flying straight into them. <p>WATCH OUT! If you wait too long, they'll shake it off, hop on their rides, and dive back into the fight.</p> </p>	
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Figure 32: QR code and visual design elements from the Tiny Conservators mediation booklet. The booklet’s visual language draws inspiration from 1990s computer game manuals, extending the playful logic of the experience beyond the digital installation. The back page links to a high-resolution Hirox scan of The Scream (MUNCH, 2024), allowing visitors to explore pigments, fibres, brushstrokes, and material damage at microscopic scale.

Observations from Live Prototype Experience

Observational feedback from museum front of house and the design team highlighted a high engagement and sustained popularity throughout the exhibition period. The simplicity of the game mechanics was repeatedly praised for making the experience accessible to a broad audience. The non-ticketed placement of the installation contributed to spontaneous participation and a diverse visitor profile.

At the same time, the intensity of use revealed practical challenges related to hardware durability and maintenance during peak periods. These observations provided valuable insights for future iterations, particularly regarding maintenance planning, staffing, and clearer guidance on acceptable levels of physical interaction in highly active public installations.

Reflection and Transferability

Beyond direct gameplay, the installation functioned as a shared social environment in which multiple forms of engagement coexisted. Active players, waiting participants, carers, and passers-by all encountered the experience simultaneously, allowing conservation themes to circulate through observation, conversation, and shared excitement. No personal data was collected during the installation, and all observations were non-intrusive and anonymous, aligning with the project's aim to support ethical and inclusive public engagement rather than formal evaluation.

As a live demonstrator within the PERCEIVE project, Tiny Conservators demonstrates how conservation science can be translated into a caring, participatory, and embodied museum experience. By combining immersive spatial design, cooperative gameplay, and tactile physical interfaces, the installation highlights the potential of games to foster care not only for cultural heritage, but also for peers and shared environments.

Replayability, Adaptation, and Transferability

Tiny Conservators was site-specific installation, but with a modular and adaptable game mechanic, and concept which can be adapted and rebuilt. At the level of gameplay, replayability is supported through cooperative dynamics, varying group compositions, and the open-ended nature of caring strategies, which encourage repeated play without a fixed or linear outcome. Visitors often returned for multiple sessions, either to try different roles or to play together with new groups.

Beyond replayability for audiences, the prototype was conceived with transferability to other museum contexts in mind. The underlying game structure allows the central artwork, narrative elements, and environmental threats to be replaced or reconfigured to address different collections, materials, or conservation challenges. While *The Scream* served as the initial case study, the concept can be adapted to other paintings or coloured heritage objects by substituting visual assets, scientific parameters, and narrative framing.

The software codebase is developed using open-source tools and will be made available via GitHub (link: <https://github.com/TEAMTOOTH/TinyConservators>), supporting reuse and experimentation by partner institutions. At the same time, meaningful implementation in other museums requires curatorial, technical, and interpretative adaptation, including alignment with local conservation research, spatial conditions, and audience needs. The physical interfaces, spatial setup, and mediation materials similarly require contextual re-design and development, rather than direct replication.

In this sense, Tiny Conservators should be understood as a design framework rather than a fixed product: a transferable approach to translating conservation science into caring, participatory experiences that can be locally re-authored. This balance between openness and contextual specificity reflects the broader PERCEIVE ambition to support sustainable, adaptable design resources for enhancing access to coloured collections across institutions.

3.2.3 PERCEIVE Fragile Colours Exhibition and Conference

Exhibition: NTNU Vitenskapsmuseet, Trondheim, Norway, 26 November 2025- 11 October 2026. The museum is attached to NTNU, and the exhibition is held in the NTNU room at the museum which seeks to

highlight the research and work of the university. The Vitenskapsmuseet, or VIMU, hosts an extensive outreach programme, and runs a large number of education programmes for school and university age students.

Conference: Victoria and Albert Museum, London, United Kingdom, 1 December 2025. The museum was a key partner in PERCEIVE and contributed expertise on autochromes based on their internationally significant collection, comprising over 2,500 plates, by among the most noted photographers and artists of the period.

The exhibition and conference sought to unite and make publicly available the outputs of the WG4 working group- historic photography and film materials- focusing on the autochrome strand. This included bringing together outputs by NTNU, Fraunhofer IGD, HSLU and the V&A. The exhibition drew on the V&A's autochrome collection, including research conducted on the plates and the presentation of large-scale facsimiles of the plates.

The exhibition, which opened 26 November 2025, invited audiences to consider ideas around how we understand, exhibit, experience and access autochromes. The exhibition opened with a lightbox, specially designed in collaboration with Catlin Langford, the V&A's Senior Conservator Mathilde Renauld and artist and designer Renato Colangelo. The lightbox featured a dimming button, light filters, a door, and an on/off switch. This meant light levels could be reduced significantly, and the lightbox could only be illuminated to a level below 100 lux. Using the lightbox set to the low lux level, two original autochromes are displayed in the exhibition. Audiences are encouraged, via clear interpretation, to open the lightbox, turn on the switch, and briefly view the original autochromes. Audiences are then directed to close the door and turn off the switch. This enables audiences to gain a wider understanding and appreciation of original autochromes and their unique materiality and quality. In addition to enabling greater audience understanding, the original autochromes are displayed with the intention of producing further research outcomes. This was an important aspect of their display. Original autochromes are commonly not exhibited by museum or heritage organisations owing to their significant light sensitivity and the potential that fading may occur. Therefore, the display of autochromes was permitted on the basis of producing new knowledge. Prior to the exhibition's opening, the Colourlab team at NTNU under Professor Giorgio Trumpy, imaged the autochromes. At the conclusion of the exhibition, the autochromes will be imaged again to ascertain if, and to what extent, the autochromes have faded, with the results published. This information will assist with future recommendations on the display of original autochromes and will be a direct result of the exhibition.

Alongside the original autochromes, interpretation was produced which highlighted the history of the process and various issues which affect the autochrome, including changes like fading. This led to an explanation of the work undertaken by the Colourlab at NTNU to digitally restore a faded autochrome. Large-scale wallpapers visually represented the various procedures undertaken by the Colourlab to separate the autochrome's gelatin silver emulsion (black and white outline) from its coloured starch granules, and the digital restoration of the coloured starch granules. A QR code was presented beside the wallpapers which led to a IIIF application developed by Dr. Yoko Arteaga which guided audiences through the process of digitally restoring an autochrome.

Audience participation and understanding was encouraged by interactives developed by Fraunhofer IGD and HSLU. A digital touchscreen offered audiences the opportunity to interact the 'degreening' application. Audiences were able to view a selection of autochromes featuring 'greening', including prominent green spotting. Through touching the screen and moving a slider across the damaged autochrome, the 'greening' would disappear, providing audiences with an impression of what the original autochrome may have looked like. The 'Autochrome Demonstrator' featured an autochrome "separated" - into the gelatin silver layer and the coloured granules layer - and printed on Perspex. When audience members view the demonstrator at a specific location, the layers combine to give a full colour image, thus enabling a greater sense of how the autochrome works.

Figure 33: Floorplans of exhibition space at VIMU, Trondheim, Norway.

Figure 34: 'Fragile Colours' installation at VIMU. The wallpaper features selected autochromes from the Victoria and Albert Museum's collection as a means of illustrating various issues which impact autochromes, including fading and the loss of emulsion.

Figure 35: ‘Fragile Colours’ installation at VIMU, presenting outputs by Fraunhofer IG, HSLU and the Colourlab at NTNU.

The exhibition is advertised on the [PERCEIVE website](#) and on the NTNU VIMU website with the abstract:

‘What are autochromes? Why do they look the way they do, and how do we best preserve fragile cultural heritage?’

The autochrome process from 1907 was the first commercially successful colour photography process, and was heralded as a revolution in photography. The process was in use in the early part of the 1900s, and was celebrated for producing luminous, painterly images.

Today, autochromes are rare and valued objects in cultural institutions. The dyes used in the autochrome plates are extremely light sensitive and fugitive, meaning that the colours tend to change or fade when exposed to light or moisture. Once the autochromes are damaged, there are limited options available for restoration. For this reason, original autochrome plates are rarely exhibited.

The PERCEIVE research group has investigated the unique materiality of autochromes, and developed new methods for restoring and exhibiting the plates, including digital solutions.

This exhibition invites you to reflect on how we understand, exhibit, experience and access fragile cultural heritage like autochromes.'

To accompany the exhibition, a day-long conference was held at the Victoria and Albert Museum, also entitled 'Fragile Colours'. The conference was also available via live-stream on Zoom, and was free to attend. The conference programme involved all parties involved with the autochrome strand of WG4 and included talks by representatives from the V&A Photography Department (Martin Barnes, Senior Curator of Photographs and Hana Kaluznick, Assistant Curator of Photographs), followed by Catlin Langford (V&A, PERCEIVE), Mathilde Renaud (Senior Conservator, V&A), Dr. Giorgio Trumpy, Dr. Irina- Mihaela Ciortan and Dr. Yoko Arteaga (Colourlab, NTNU), Arthur Clay (HSLU), and Saptarshi Neil Sinha (Fraunhofer IG). Each session was followed by questions from the audience in person and online, chaired by Dr Lucia Burgo (Lead Conservation Scientist, V&A). The conference was attended by over 150 people.

'Fragile Colours: Perceiving and Experiencing Autochromes' conference and workshop at the Victoria and Albert Museum, London on 1 December 2025

3.2.4 PERCEIVE Open Space Museum

3.2.4.1 A Ticket to the Moon

A Ticket to the Moon – Testing OSM Social Elements as “Social Plastics” (Max Frisch Areal / Letzigraben-Bad, Zürich, September–December 2025)

Format: Public exhibition / site-specific installation (social-element field test)

Place: AQUARIUM / gallery space at the Letzigraben complex (Max Frisch Areal), Zürich, Switzerland

Audience: General public; cultural-sector stakeholders; local visitors (incl. hosted tours on Sundays)

More info: <https://mondticket.blogspot.com/p/concept.html>

Event description:

A Ticket to the Moon functioned primarily as a real-world test of the Open Space Museum’s Social Elements understood as Social Plastics in the sense of Joseph Beuys’ “Soziale Plastik”: sculptural interventions that do not merely occupy space, but actively shape social relations, participation, and forms of co-presence. The exhibition therefore focused on how bodily comfort, playful action, shared attention, and informal conversation can be designed as curatorial material—turning the visitor’s behaviour itself into the medium through which meaning is produced.

Rather than treating the installation as a sequence of objects to observe, the configuration was built around rest, proximity, and interaction as the primary mechanism of engagement. Hammock-based constellations and reduced sound-interaction elements were deployed as social catalysts, inviting visitors to pause, recline, listen, and negotiate shared use of the space. These Social Elements were evaluated as behavioural “forms” that generate micro-communities: temporary assemblies of strangers who become co-participants through simple acts of resting, playing, and exchanging impressions.

Digital content (including optional AR access points) operated as a secondary layer that could be activated through the social situation, not as the main attraction. In this way, the exhibition tested a core Open Space Museum hypothesis: that social form—not only media content—can be designed, staged, and assessed as a dissemination strategy, enabling public encounters with PERCEIVE themes through lived, embodied participation.

Lessons learned (social usefulness + performance use)

A Ticket to the Moon served as a field test of the Open Space Museum’s social elements (hammock constellations) not only as visitor-facing resting interfaces, but as enabling infrastructure for external artistic practices. The installation provided a spatial and social “stage” (backdrop / place of action) that invited a group of external artists to appropriate the hammocks as scenography and to reinterpret the narrative frame (*Goddesses and Their Lovers*) through their own performative languages. The performances did not illustrate the installation but reimaged and retooled it, using the Social Elements as material for independent artistic practice.

In parallel, visitors were invited to use the hammocks in the most direct way—as hammocks—allowing observation of the practical and bodily aspects of engagement (e.g., how people enter and exit, balance, comfort, confidence) as well as the affective and social implications of performing an everyday act of rest within a gallery context. This deliberate shift of context (discontextualisation) exposed a productive tension between ordinary bodily action and the expectations of an art space.

Taken together, these observations revealed how the same Social Elements can operate across two complementary modes—(1) as a reusable basis for co-created performance and (2) as a simple, embodied social interface for visitors—thereby validating the Open Space Museum as a participation prototype. The test demonstrated that social form can function as an infrastructural condition for participation and as a host for third-party cultural activities, rather than as a fixed or closed artwork.

Key Social Elements tested (Social Plastics):

- **Hammock constellations (“Goddesses and Their Lovers”)** as a structured social resting field (pairing, solitude, proximity, and relational positioning).
- **HörRoom (reduced)** as a playful sound-based participation trigger supporting shared attention and interaction.
- **Supporting access points** (where applicable) linking the social situation to optional digital/AR layers.

Taken together, these Social Elements were treated as sculptural parameters for shaping behaviour—inviting visitors to slow down, share space, and negotiate participation through simple, bodily actions. In this sense, *A Ticket to the Moon* operated as a practical validation of the Open Space Museum thesis that dissemination can be built not only through information delivery, but through the design of social form: a curated situation in which care, attention, and co-presence become the medium through which cultural meaning is produced.

Figure 36: Element of the exhibition *A Ticket to the Moon* (credits: <https://mondticket.blogspot.com/p/artworks.html>)

4 Catalogue of tools, prototypes and demonstrators

PERCEIVE has produced a catalogue of demonstrators accessible directly from the project website and available at this link [PERCEIVE Tool & Demonstrators - PERCEIVE](#). It is a **web-based collection of the tools, services and prototypes**, produced by WP5 and WP6. The catalogue includes descriptions, video tutorials, publications and dissemination material. The content of the catalogue, the tools and prototypes, will be used in the final events. Most of Tools and Services will be also used by expert, although not exclusively, to create the Prototypes for the general public.

A full description of Tools and Services is included in Deliverable 5.1 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10658217>) and Deliverable 4.1.

The project developed a set of digital and hybrid prototypes addressing priority concepts such as “authenticity”, “care”, and “participation”; while these prototypes have been thoroughly analysed in Deliverable 6.1, their main characteristics are summarised here, with the Open Space Museum (OSM) conceived as a participation prototype and design framework from which specific installations and events derive as field tests and instantiations rather than standalone demonstrators.

1. **The authenticity prototype:** based on the concept of authenticity, its three dimensions (the self, the other and the world) and their respective characteristics, this prototype aims at touching the deeper self of the user, through performative actions that transform what is perceived as distant and unfamiliar, into something closer and familiar. It is thought to incorporate both physical and virtual elements, to adapt to different context (on site and remote) and to support multi-user collaboration.
2. **The caring prototype:** based on the concept of caring intended as a deliberate and action-oriented event that revolves around showing kindness, concern, and consideration towards others, actively supporting their well-being. This translates in an interactive digital and hybrid experience designed for both citizens and visitors, whether inside or outside a museum context, with the goal of fostering a personal and profound connection with coloured collections by raising awareness of colour fragility and cultivating a sense of belonging, enchantment, and care.
3. **The participation or open space museum prototype:** based on the pioneering initiative of adopting a “phygital” approach, seamlessly blending digital and physical elements to create distinctive visitor experiences. Its core objectives include enhancing the cultural experience for the public, promoting civic participation and influencing cultural progress while contributing to sustainability through inventive methods.

A full description of the prototypes is included in Deliverable 6.1 PERCEIVE Concept Design, UX and Design Brief (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10658273>).

These prototypes have been designed following a user-oriented and a “modular” approach. The modular approach is meant to demonstrate how different types of experiences could have an impact on the cognitive-emotional engagement of the visitors.

Within the project's first year, we have successfully developed initial demonstrators dedicated for Autochromes, for Lenticular Film, for Colour Perception beyond Visual Means, a Sketch Book showing detailed designs for the Open Space Museum, and a VR Demonstrator portraying the design approach and content for the Chroma Elements of the Open Space Museum.

5 Conclusions

This Deliverable has presented the dissemination outcomes developed within WP8 of the PERCEIVE project, documenting both the strategic planning and the concrete implementation of publications, events, exhibitions,

and demonstrators. D8.3 reflects the progressive consolidation of PERCEIVE's dissemination approach, integrating scientific research, design practices, and public engagement into a coherent framework.

Over the course of the project, PERCEIVE has delivered a significant body of open-access publications, including two edited volumes and an exhibition catalogue, ensuring the wide circulation of scientific results and methodological frameworks. The first book "Chromatic Visions" explores colour's theoretical foundations, from classical antiquities to modern art and textiles, emphasizing care, authenticity, and civic participation, while the second focused on technological aspects, will be released in the project's third year, ensuring the dissemination of tools and prototypes which were developed in the PERCEIVE project.

In parallel, the organisation of scientific events and hybrid exhibitions has enabled the translation of complex research on colour change, fragility, and perception into accessible and engaging formats for diverse audiences.

The project's presence at major international forums, most notably the Digital Heritage International Congress 2025 in Siena, provided a platform for the consortium to present its groundbreaking tools and give a glimpse of its prototypes, demonstrating the project's success in bridging the gap between high-level laboratory research and user-friendly digital solutions for heritage professionals.

A central achievement of this final phase has been the physical and digital implementation of the project's prototypes through a series of significant exhibitions and interactive experiences. These include the PERCEIVE Isis' Colours exhibition ("The Gifts of Isis" for the Authenticity Prototype and "Echoes of Loss" for the Caring Prototype) presented at the Digital Heritage International Congress 2025 in Siena and ArcheoVirtual (BMTA 2025) in Paestum; the "Tiny Conservators" (Caring Prototype) cooperative game developed for the MUNCH in Oslo; the 'Fragile Colours' exhibition at the VIMU in Trondheim, uniting research and outputs relating to the autochrome and making these accessible and available to the public for a year-long period; the 'Fragile Colours' conference at the Victoria and Albert Museum in London; and the Open Space Museum exhibited at Zurich revolutionizing community interactions with art and culture with its modules that provide immersive and educational experiences for all, bridging physical and virtual realms.

These results, combined with a significant body of open-access publications and the Catalogue of Demonstrators, provide a solid foundation for the long-term sustainability of the project's findings. The validity of these interventions has been confirmed by professional recognition and national media coverage, ensuring that the methodologies developed for studying and communicating colour, from classical polychromy to digital-born art, remain a lasting reference for the heritage sector.